

Striving for Sustainable Development of Ukraine: Guest Editorial

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Abstract

The special issue on the Sustainable Development of Ukraine aims to study the multidimensional nature of ensuring Ukraine's sustainable development and develop practical recommendations for overcoming challenges by integrating scientific achievements, technological innovations, and management strategies. The objectives of the special issue are to study the role and analyse the prospects for the introduction of innovative technologies and digitalization in ensuring the sustainability of the Ukrainian economy; to analyze the regulatory framework and political mechanisms aimed at shaping a sustainable development strategy in Ukraine; to study environmental approaches and analyse the state and key stages of the implementation of the circular economy; to identify social aspects and develop practical solutions for priority areas of social impact, in particular, education, emotional intelligence and social inclusion.

The rapid expansion of industry and the ongoing exploitation of natural resources to meet humanity's growing needs have highlighted the urgent need for a qualitative shift in the international order. This new approach should focus on transforming the global ecosystem into a framework where humanity and the environment coexist harmoniously, ensuring that human priorities do not compromise the preservation, renewal, and sustainable use of limited natural resources. Consequently, environmental protection has become a critical issue not only in the political arena but also as an existential challenge intertwined with regional and national interests, ultimately carrying significant global implications. Sustainable development represents a balanced interaction between society and nature, safeguarding the survival of humanity while preserving the environment. It aims to meet the needs of the present generation without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This principle now underpins policymaking in the United States, Canada, Japan, the European Union, and numerous other countries, including those in the developing world.

The sustainable development paradigm emerged in response to widespread environmental degradation and the urgent need to address global threats to ecosystems and human health at the close of the 20th century. In modern Ukraine, the implementation of this paradigm is influenced not only by global environmental and social challenges but also by the profound consequences of the full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation in early 2022. Since the drafting of the initial *Law on the Concept of Sustainable Development of Ukraine* (No. 3234, dated April 25, 2001), numerous efforts and extensive consultations have sought to define key priorities for sustainable development, establish a national framework, create a legal basis for transitioning to sustainable development principles, and develop relevant indicators. However, the first comprehensive document outlining Ukraine's strategic approach to long-term development was the *Decree of the President of Ukraine* "On the Strategy of Sustainable Development 'Ukraine - 2020'" (No. 5/2015, January 12, 2015), followed by the *Decree of the President of Ukraine* "On the Sustainable Development Goals of Ukraine for the

Period up to 2030” (No. 722/2019, September 30, 2019). Despite these efforts, a lack of an effective state regulatory model persists—one that integrates economic growth, social equity, and sustainable use of natural resources. This gap is highlighted in subsection 2.1 of Section 2 of the ISES Analytical Report, *Analysis of State Strategic Documents on the Adaptation to Global Challenges*. Additionally, ongoing scientific discourse and international experience underscore the absence of universal approaches and tools for achieving sustainable development. This further emphasizes the need for continued research and the development of innovative strategies to refine and implement the sustainable development paradigm, both in Ukraine and globally.

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The relevance of the special issue is to identify strategic directions for achieving sustainable development in Ukraine in the face of the extraordinary challenges of our time. The beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine has led to several significant negative factors, including a decrease in the level of security for the population, destruction of infrastructure, loss of human resources, and the performance of business entities in a changing business environment. The foremost opportunity for a rapid and high-quality recovery of the business sector is the implementation of sustainable development measures. Ukraine's sustainable economic development in the context of the war and the subsequent post-war period is primarily determined by the availability of the country's internal resources and the ability of government agencies to influence the cohesion of society, effectively apply financial and economic levers to regulate development, timely identify threats and ensure the implementation of changes to prevent or mitigate their negative consequences. Therefore, the articles presented in the special issue cover various aspects of sustainable development, which allow us to systematize challenges, identify key priorities and ensure a comprehensive approach to their solution.

The legal aspect of the article on the topic "Using Renewable Energy for Sustainable Economic Growth and Environmental Sustainability" indicates the need to eliminate the consequences of climate change by strengthening the legislative support for the implementation of renewable energy. In this context, the authors identify a clear and effective legal framework as a prerequisite for improving the stability of the energy sector, along with balanced public policy and investment attractiveness. The article "Regulatory and Institutional Frameworks for Ensuring Financial Security in Ukraine's Energy Sector: Challenges and Future Outlook" examines the regulatory and institutional aspects necessary to ensure Ukraine's energy security. It also emphasizes

Ukraine's integration into the European Energy Space for infrastructure modernization and financial security in the energy sector. The article on the topic "Policy and Legal Framework for the Formation of Effective Sustainable Development Management Strategies in a Geographical Context" assesses the policy and legal mechanisms for activating green technologies and sustainable development. Based on the article's results, the authors propose ways to eliminate inequality in access to resources and global crises by involving the public in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. In the document "The Role of the Circular Economy in Promoting Environmentally Sustainable Industrial Production", the authors propose solutions to strengthen the regulatory policy of resource efficiency and sustainable development to eliminate the shortcomings of the current legislative framework in Ukraine. The article "Social Integration in Stimulating Sustainable Development of United Territorial Communities" examines solutions for strengthening joint governance in united territorial communities. The article "Legal Protection of the Environment in Wartime: Theoretical and Practical Analysis" analyses mechanisms for compensation for damage caused by military actions and recommendations for post-war environmental policy, including compliance with EU standards on environmental safety.

The economic aspect is traced in the paper "Assessing the Impact of Green Taxation Policies on Sustainable Growth", which assesses the impact of environmental taxation policies on sustainable economic practices. The authors of this article emphasize the ability of the leading EU companies to boost investments in renewable energy and environmental taxes to promote sustainability in the context of globalization and the aggravation of environmental problems. The study "Agricultural Technologies as a Tool for Integrating Artificial Intelligence into the Agricultural Infrastructure of Ukraine" considers IoT, robotics and precision farming as key drivers of economic growth and environmental balance. The article's authors contribute to the scientific debate on resource efficiency and the economy's global competitiveness through agricultural technologies. Another innovation is artificial intelligence, which is analyzed in the article "Artificial Intelligence in Waste Management in the Context of Implementing Circular Economy". The authors of this article argue that the current state of the processing industry in Ukraine is unsatisfactory. However, reducing waste incineration and operating expenses makes it possible to achieve rapid growth in this sector, thus advancing the national waste management strategy. The paper "The Role of Innovation Parks in Stimulating Digital Achievements and Promoting Energy Efficiency" examines the role of innovation parks in providing a platform for implementing such innovations. In addition to fostering innovation, it is important to mitigate risks related to climate change and adapt business processes to its impacts, as highlighted in the article "Developing strategies for adapting business processes to climate change: minimizing risks in the context of global climate challenges". The article focuses on issues of flexibility and planning and outlines the main strategies that contribute to the coherence of corporate operations with current environmental uncertainty. Therefore, the authors argue that risk reduction initiatives' resource potential and investment planning should be assessed to ensure business resilience. The article "Ensuring Sustainable Development of the Agricultural Sector through Financial Instruments in the Context of Climate Change" demonstrates the effectiveness of financial instruments in increasing the resilience of the agricultural sector to climate change and promoting the productivity of companies. The authors of the article "Ukraine's Role in Ensuring Global Food

Security: Current Challenges and Prospects" examined Ukraine's experience as a key global food supplier in the context of the need to increase the productivity of the agricultural sector and resilience to geopolitical challenges.

The environmental aspect is evident in the study "Review of Innovative Approaches to Sustainable Use of Ukraine's Natural Resources". The article analyses Ukraine's energy sector, emphasizing the role of renewable sources in decarbonization and ecosystem preservation during post-war reconstruction. However, in another article, "Development of Renewable Energy Sources: Impact on Sustainability and the Environment", the authors focused on the benefits of renewable energy in solving global energy problems. The article "Advancing Waste Reduction and Resource Conservation through Circular Economy Practices: A Rational Review" aims to study the circular economy regarding waste minimization and conservation of natural resources.

The social aspect is also considered in several papers in this issue. The article "Leveraging Media and Public Relations Strategies to Advance Sustainable Development: Approaches, Frameworks, Tactics in Modern Conditions" examines innovative methods of communication, the dynamics of trust in the media, and the characteristics of the formation of environmental awareness and corporate responsibility. The article "The Role of Communication in Developing Environmental Awareness and Concern for Environmental Problems" demonstrates the potential of communication to increase public awareness of environmental problems. The research found that digital platforms possess a distinct advantage over traditional media, making them more effective in promoting environmental consciousness. The findings of the work "Typological Model of How Civil Servants Develop Emotional Intelligence in Ukraine" offer recommendations for improving emotional resilience and decision-making by civil servants. The article "Pedagogical Approaches to Educating Environmental Awareness of Students of Higher Educational Institutions" discusses environmental awareness. It aims to convey the values of sustainable development to students and prepare them for the professional role of environmentally conscious citizens.

The special issue highlights the challenges confronting Ukraine's sustainable development, which is currently mired in a prolonged armed conflict. This issue presents research on social components, economic instability, legal assistance, and environmental awareness. The findings presented in this special issue aim to provide novel prospects for implementing novel technologies, enhance the legal framework, and enhance public support for sustainable development. The authors present systemic resolutions for resolving and adapting contemporary issues in the specialized issue. This special issue of GJNR offers various scientific strategies and valuable suggestions for boosting public awareness, bolstering the legal framework, and implementing fresh concepts. This issue contributes significantly to the scientific discourse aimed at ensuring the sustainable functioning of Ukraine during times of war and its postwar recovery and ensuring the quality of the Sustainable Development Goals.

- Prof. Dr. Zoriana Buryk
Guest Editor for Special Issue